

The depth wise enrichment of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn) in sewage irrigated soils of Allahabad

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Abstract : The depth wise enrichment of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Cu and Zn) were studied in different profiles of sewage irrigated soils of Allahabad. The representative soil samples were collected from three different sites. The samples were collected from different depth, i.e. 0-10, 10-20, 20-30 and 30-40 cm. Maximum accumulation of heavy metals was observed in Naini sewage farm whereas, Baxi Bandh was second in order. Phaphamau soil was least polluted in comparison to Naini sewage farm and Baxi Bandh soil. Heavy metals may persist in soil for a much longer time and may result in phytotoxicity. Therefore, a proper monitoring of sewage irrigated soils is required in order to control metallic pollution of soil.

Keywords : Heavy metals, sewage-sludge, accumulation.

Introduction

Disposal of sewage-sludge has received much attention as huge amount of these wastes are being produced by urban and industrial activities. As a consequence of these activities, the heavy metal concentration of soils has increased wide world¹. Municipal sludge often contains undesirable chemicals which may be toxic to plants and/or eventually toxic to animals and human that consumes edible parts of such plants². Heavy metals accumulate at soil surface through the sewage-sludge application. There is evidence of considerable movement of Zn and to a lesser extent of Cd and Ni, to depths below 15 cm as a result of repeated irrigation for about 70 years with liquid raw sewage; apparently Pb and Cu did not so move³. In natural soil profiles cadmium and lead accumulated in the upper part of soil profiles, and distribution pattern of these elements was similar to that of organic matter⁴. Application of sewage water for irrigation purpose has increased over the past years. This waste contains high amount of trace elements and heavy metals. Waste water are contaminated with trace elements like lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), mercury (Hg), uranium (U), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), boron (B), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), molybdenum (Mo) etc. Many of these are non-essential and toxic to plants, animals and human beings. Waste water is suitable for irrigation if the

content of toxic elements reduced considerably⁵. In a soil receiving annual application of sludge, about 50% the added Zn and Cd had moved to depths below 15 cm during the 6 years after the first application⁶. The total amount of individual heavy metals in soil solution are usually low. The metal availability (or solubility) depends on a number of factors, including type of colloid, presence of soluble organic ligands, pH, microbial activity, redox potential and aeration⁷. The objective of all case studies was to study wastewater use in a holistic way, looking at environmental and health risks. To this study components were implemented including a cross-sectional health survey to estimate the heavy metals highly leached in sub soil. Application of wastewater irrigation, a soil and crop survey looking at soil and crop heavy metal concentrations and potential human food chain contamination risks.

Keeping in view the adverse effects of heavy metal accumulation in soil profiles, an attempt has been made to assess the metallic build-up in soils.

Results and discussion

The distribution of four major pollutants was as follows :

Cadmium : It was observed that the total Cd in sewage irrigated soils is always higher than in the non-sewage

irrigated soils. The total Cd concentration in different soils, irrigated with sewage water ranged from 0.2 to 5.1 mg kg⁻¹, against 0.2 to 1.6 mg kg⁻¹ in non-sewage irrigated soils (Table 1). Extractable (available) cadmium also varied in sewage irrigated and non-sewage irrigated soils. In sewage irrigated soils, the amount of DTPA-extractable Cd is much more than in non-sewage irrigated soil. These results indicate that the nature and quality of sewage water affect the availability of Cd in soil.

Copper : Total Cu concentration in all the soil samples irrigated with sewage water is much higher than the non-sewage irrigated soils. It is further noticed that extractable Cu concentration vary much higher in sewage irrigated and in non-sewage irrigated soil samples from Phaphamau sewage farm and Baxi Bandh sewage farm, whereas samples from Naini sewage soil exhibit variable results. It is clear from Table 1 that extractable Cu is affected by the type of the soil. Phaphamau sewage farm

Table 1. Enrichment of heavy metals in sewage irrigated and in non-sewage irrigated soil of Phaphamou, Naini and Baxi Bandh sewage farm (mg kg⁻¹)

	Phaphamau sewage farm							
	Cd		Cu		Pb		Zn	
	Total	DTPA-extractable	Total	DTPA-extractable	Total	DTPA-extractable	Total	DTPA-extractable
Sewage irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	5.1	0.32	66.00	0.56	4.2	2.3	105	2.23
A ₂ 10-20	4.4	0.15	64.86	0.52	3.2	1.6	164	1.05
A ₃ 20-30	4.2	0.13	88.98	0.34	3.0	1.2	132	1.45
A ₄ 30-40	1.4	0.11	98.64	0.30	1.4	0.8	124	1.75
Non-sewage irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	1.6	0.02	62.45	0.58	1.01	0.82	102	0.11
A ₂ 10-20	0.63	0.14	61.42	0.62	0.93	0.35	118	0.25
A ₃ 20-30	1.3	0.03	96.68	0.32	0.41	0.17	132	0.15
A ₄ 30-40	0.56	0.02	102.0	0.29	0.37	0.07	115	0.11
Naini sewage farm								
Sewage-irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	4.4	2.7	88.86	0.52	3.8	2.4	106.00	0.62
A ₂ 10-20	2.3	2.1	68.00	0.50	3.3	1.8	96.00	0.60
A ₃ 20-30	1.8	0.7	88.44	0.48	2.5	1.4	86.00	0.42
A ₄ 30-40	1.1	0.2	88.82	0.34	1.2	0.8	82.00	0.31
Non-sewage irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	1.01	0.76	85.42	0.49	1.02	0.81	75.00	2.01
A ₂ 10-20	0.97	0.11	90.24	0.31	0.91	0.31	79.00	0.83
A ₃ 20-30	0.21	0.05	88.45	0.44	0.46	0.15	77.00	0.53
A ₄ 30-40	0.51	0.03	85.36	0.45	0.37	0.07	75.00	0.72
Baxi Bandh sewage farm								
Sewage irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	2.24	1.5	100.64	4.13	3.9	2.4	101.00	6.22
A ₂ 10-20	1.34	0.5	94.46	3.18	2.8	1.8	96.00	3.50
A ₃ 20-30	0.82	0.2	96.84	3.46	2.4	1.2	86.00	4.22
A ₄ 30-40	0.25	0.07	101.82	4.23	1.2	0.9	98.00	2.21
Non-sewage irrigated :								
A ₁ 0-10	0.7	0.3	68.74	0.36	1.01	0.70	103.00	2.63
A ₂ 10-20	1.0	0.3	68.58	0.38	0.91	0.33	100.20	2.71
A ₃ 20-30	0.3	N.D.	86.52	0.34	0.41	0.15	68.62	2.11
A ₄ 30-40	0.2	N.D.	96.40	0.32	0.35	0.08	62.50	1.60

and Baxi Bandh sewage farm soils are dumped soils whereas Naini soils are normal soils receiving sewage water. Total Cu content increased with depth from 68 to 106 mg kg⁻¹ and 60 to 102 mg kg⁻¹ in 0–40 cm depth in sewage irrigated soil and in normal soil.

Lead : Total Pb concentration in almost all soil samples irrigated with sewage water is much higher than the non-sewage irrigated soil. Total Pb content decreased with depth from 4.2 to 1.01 mg kg⁻¹ and 1.02 to 0.35 mg kg⁻¹ in 0–40 cm depth in sewage irrigated soil and in normal soil respectively. Extractable Pb also decreased with depth in both sewage irrigated soil and in normal soils.

Zinc : In case of Zn, there is not much variation in total Zn in sewage irrigated and in non-sewage irrigated soil samples. But available Zn varies in all the samples. Extractable Zn in sewage irrigated soil is always more than three times that of non-sewage irrigated soils. The increased level of available Zn may, therefore, be inferred to be due to sewage irrigation alone. Most of the sewage irrigated soils contain high amount of total Zn in the sewage (85.21 to 161 mg kg⁻¹). Total Zn shows variable distribution pattern, but DTPA-Zn always decreases with increase in soil depth. In normal soil, total Zn decreased after the 20–30 cm depth. Extractable Zn decreased with increased in the soil depth.

Colloidal organic matter has a strong affinity for heavy metal cations and the retention of added metals is often well correlated with the amount of soil organic matter⁸. Organic matter may provide sites for cation exchange reaction but its strong affinity for heavy metal cations is due to ligands or groups that form chelates and/or complexes with the metals⁹. The retaining ability of organic matter for heavy metals is predominantly through its CEC property rather than chelating ability, and Cd has a tendency to combine with certain chelating groups and become fixed¹⁰.

The sub soil can remove a large proportion of any heavy metal that remains in solution in the downward moving water. As the content of organic matter generally decreases with depth in the profile, the removal is attributable to the increasing content and/or activity of the inorganic colloids. Any downward movement of metals leaching will also be influenced by soil physical properties, including texture and permeability as well as by climate and seasonal variation in rainfall and evaporation⁸.

The significant factors influencing the availability of heavy metals are soil pH and the quality of soil organic matter^{11,12}.

Extent of contamination :

The ratio of metals contents in A₁ versus A₄ horizon can serve as an index of contamination in sewage-sludge irrigated soils. The ratio values greater than 1 indicate metal accumulation in the soil irrigated with sewage water.

The data given in Table 2 indicate that the Naini sewage farm soil was highly polluted whereas the Baxi Bandli sewage farm soil second in order. Phaphamau sewage

Table 2. Ratios of heavy metals in A₁ vs A₄ horizon in sewage water irrigated soils

Profile location	Heavy metals (mg kg ⁻¹)			
	Cd	Cu	Pb	Zn
Phaphamau sewage farm	3.60	0.67	1.77	0.85
Baxi Bandh sewage farm	4.00	0.98	3.16	1.03
Naini sewage farm	8.96	1.00	3.25	1.29

farm soil was least polluted in comparison to Naini sewage farm and Baxi Bandh sewage farm soil. A low downward movement of heavy metals in all the soil is indicator of its accumulation in the top layer. The Cd and Pb accumulate in soil as a result of repeated application of sewage-sludge over a long period.

The high concentrations of extractable heavy metals in surface soils will not only reduce the plant growth but will also affect the availability of other essential elements of plants. Vegetables grown on such soil are liable to contain higher concentration of these heavy metals which are injurious to health.

Materials and methods :

Soil samples were collected from three selected sites known to have used sewage irrigation. These sites were Phaphamou sewage farm, Baxi Bandh sewage farm and Naini sewage farm, Allahabad. The samples were collected from different depths i.e. 0–10, 10–20, 20–30 and 30–40 cm. The soils of these selected sites are composed mostly of recent and old alluvium (ENTISOLS) with some filler soil. A detailed study for the movement of heavy metals in sewage irrigated soils was taken up. The soil samples, after being brought to the laboratory, were air-dried, powdered with a wooden hammer and sieved through a 2 mm sieve and stored. The representative soil samples were analysed for four heavy metals i.e. Cd, Cu,

Pb and Zn. For the total content of these heavy metals, soil samples were extracted with di-acid mixture and for the available content, samples were extracted with diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) solution was prepared to extract the available heavy metals in soil samples¹³. Soil pH was estimated in the 1 : 2.5 (soil : water) suspension using glass electrode pH meter. Organic carbon was determined by chromic acid digestion method¹⁴ and CEC by using neutral ammonium acetate solution¹³.

Heavy metals were analysed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model-Pye Unicam SP 2900 coupled with SP-9 computer and Induced Couple Plasma Model-LABTEM).

Physico-chemical characteristics of the sewage irrigated soil as well as non-sewage irrigated from three different sites are given Table 3.

Table 3. Physico-chemical characteristics of the soil (sewage-irrigated)

	Location		
	Phaphamou sewage farm	Baxi Bandh sewage farm	Naini sewage farm
pH	7.5 (7.3) ^a	7.3 (7.1)	8.2 (7.6)
Organic carbon (%)	1.20 (0.45)	0.87 (0.57)	0.95 (0.61)
CEC [Cmol (P ⁺) Kg ⁻¹]	26.7 (17.7)	22.6 (13.5)	30.1 (28.2)
Soil texture	Sandy loam	Loam	Sandy

^aRepresents non-sewage irrigated soil.

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References

1. D. C. Adriano, "Trace Elements in the Terrestrial Environments", Springer, New York, 2001.
2. E. Epstein, *Environ. Qual. J.*, 1975, **4**, 139.
3. G. W. Leeper, "Managing the Metals on Land", Dekker, New York, 1978.
4. A. Anderson, *J. Agric.*, 1977, Res. 7,7.
5. J. S. Kanwar and M. S. Sandha, *Agricultural Reviews*, 2000, **21**, 133.
6. T. D. Hinesly, R. L. Jones, R. L. Ziegler, E. L. and J. I. Tyier, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1978, **11**, 182.
7. L. H. P. Jones and S. C. Jarvis, "The Fate of Heavy Metal", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1981, p. 593.
8. J. F. Hodgson, *Adv. Agron.*, 1963, **15**, 119.
9. F. J. Stevenson, M. S. Ardakani, J. J. Mortvedt, P. M. Giordano and W. L. Lrndsay, Soil Science Society of America Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA, 1972, p. 79.
10. F. Haghiri, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1974, **3**, 180.
11. G. Barancikova and J. Makovnikov, *Plant Soil Environ.*, 2003, **49**, 565.
12. M. Puschenreiter, O. Horak, W. Friesl and W. Hartl, *Plant Soil Environ.*, 2005, **51**, 1.
13. W. L. Lindsay and W. A. Norvell, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 1978, **42**, 421.
14. A. Walkley and I. A. Black, *Soil Science*, 1934, **37**, 29.
15. L. A. Richards, USDA Handbook No. 60, Washington DC, 1954, pp. 7.